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ABSTRACTS

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participation more actively. The modified MMT was performed to evaluate the muscle strength of quadriceps femoris, tibialis anterior, and other clinical evaluations were performed to assess the motor function with gross motor function measure (GMFM). *Results:* The muscle strength of quadriceps femoris increased from 2+–3+ grades to 4–5 grades and the tibialis anterior increased from 1–2 grades to 3–4 grades, there was significant difference with muscle strength ($p < 0.05$). There was also significant improvement in the score of GMFM. *Implications:* The play therapy for children with spastic cerebral palsy can improve the muscle strength, as well as the motor function of lower extremities. By the way, the CP children participate the treatment easier and improve the movement function during a happy treatment.

PO-1092

INFLUENCE OF INFRA-LOW-FREQUENCY TRANSCRANIAL MAGNETIC STIMULATION ON MOTOR FUNCTION IN CHILDREN WITH SPASTIC CEREBRAL PALSY

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Objective: To investigate the effects of infra-low-frequency transcranial magnetic stimulation on motor function in children with spastic cerebral palsy. *Methods:* The children with spastic cerebral palsy were randomly divided into two groups, control group and treatment group. The control group only accepted conventional comprehensive rehabilitation and the treatment group accepted infra-low-frequency transcranial magnetic stimulation during comprehensive rehabilitative training, evaluating children with gross motor function measure (GMFM) and fine motor function measure (FMFM) after the first month and the third month, comparing the difference of improvement in motor function between two groups, to observe the effects of infra-low-frequency transcranial magnetic stimulation. *Results:* The improvement of sitting, crawling and kneeling area with GMFM in the treatment group was better than the control group after treatment with three months. The improvement of joint active ability of limbs, grasping ability, operating ability with FMFM in the treatment group was better than the control group after treatment with three months. *Implication:* Infra-low-frequency transcranial magnetic stimulation can effectively improve the motor function of children with spastic cerebral palsy.

PO-1093

THE EFFECT OF EARLY INTERVENTION ON NSCS DIFFERENTIATION OF DENTATE GYRUS

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Objective: To study the impact of early intervention on differentiation of neural stem cells (NSCs) in brain damage rats after HIBD (Hypoxic-ischemic brain injury). *Methods:* Totally 75 SD (Sprague Dawley) rats aged 7 days were randomly divided into two groups: HIBD model ($n=50$) and sham-operated ($n=25$). 50 HIBD model was produced with Rice method, and randomly divided into HIBD group ($n=25$) and early intervention group ($n=25$). HIBD group and sham-operated group are normally feed, intervention group are dealt with early intervention, 5 rats were killed at 1 day, 7 days, 14 days, 21 days and 28 days after operation in each group. Each rat was injected with BrdU into its abdominal cavity to mark new cells before killed. Double staining immunofluorescence was used to detect the co-expression of bromodeoxyuridine (BrdU) with neuronal nuclei antigen (NeuN) or glia fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) in the Dentate gyrus (DG) at different time points. *Result:* (1) BrdU/NeuN and BrdU/GFAP double staining cells were observed in all 3 groups. (2) In the HIBD and intervention groups, at 14, 21 and 28

days after the surgery, the number of BrdU/NeuN and BrdU/GFAP double-stained cells increased in the DG compared with the sham-operated group ($p < 0.01$). (3) Obviously more BrdU/NeuN and BrdU/GFAP double-stained cells were found in the early intervention group than that in the HIBD group at 14, 21 and 28 days ($p < 0.01$). *Implication:* Our results indicate that the brain damage caused by HIBD can induce the differentiation of endogenous NSCs: Early intervention can increase the differentiation of endogenous NSCs.

PO-1094

DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINE MOTORIC IN THE CHILDREN 2-3 YEARS OLDER THROUGH THE PLAY

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Objective: At the age 2-3 children learn to identify, recognize and named different basic shapes. During the play children developed and strength musculoskeletal system, improve basic movement, coordination, eye-hand and stimulated development of both hemisphere of the brain. *Methods:* In the project was participated 38 children (girls 24 and boys 14), age 20-32 (average 26, 84) months. Children were educated about different basic shapes (circle, triangle and square) through the play "learning shape". After that each child made its individual work- making in collage technique "carpet of shape" from learned basic shapes in 3 min period. *Results:* Making "carpet of shape" children used from 16 to 43 shapes (average 26,7). We could not find statistically significant correlation between sex and number of used elements ($r=0.03$; $p=0.896$) and age and number of used elements ($r=0.23$; $p=0.337$). The most common used shape was circle 10,10 (from 3 to 21), less common used was square 8,74 (from 0 to 9) and the least common used was triangle 7,89 (from 0 to 8) which was statistically significant (for triangle $r=0.696$; $p=0.001$ and for square $r=0.539$; $p=0.017$). There were not statistically significance between use of different kind of shape and age (circle $r=0.1541$; $p=0.529$, square $r=-0.0092$; $p=0.970$ and triangle $r=0.2543$; $p=0.293$). *Implication on Rehabilitation:* Activities were pleasant and interesting for children Usage round shape object can stimulated development of fine motoric abilities, children curiosity and new perception experiences, connecting motoric and cognitive child function, giving the possibility to detect and correct problems in their development.

PO-1095

THE RESEARCH PROGRESS OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDY OF CEREBRAL PALSY

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The epidemiologic study can help to find the etiological clues of cerebral palsy and provide the evidence, so it also is beneficial to establish the control network. The prevalence rate of cerebral palsy may be affected by biological factors, diagnostic codediagnostic code, the level of diagnosis. These factors are associated with diversity of the prevalence rate. Risk factors for prenatal are the most common, for example low birth weight and low gestational age. Cerebral palsy of premature infants are most based on spastic type, while full-term infants with cerebral palsy mainly manifested as non spastic type, and their motor disorders more easily seriously.

PO-1096

THE QUALITY OF LIFE AND ITS INFLUENCING FACTORS FOR MOTHERS OF CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

Xia Huang